

Secure Group Key Management for Group Communication in IoMT Environment with Dual Encryption Scheme

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Abstract. Internet of Things (IoT) role is inevitable in today's scenario. The secure communication between IoT devices is given much importance. This study proposes a group key management approach with dual encryption scheme (AES and RSA) to ensure secure group communication. The doctors and devices /patients are the members (components) of the communication network and the data is exchanged between the devices and authenticated doctors. The group key along with the Identity key is utilized here to establish secure group communication between the members. The group key management ensures security, thereby avoiding the hacking of data. The group key is considered to be valid in group communication for a maximum time period (72 hrs). The proposed group communication model is implemented for Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) environment using dual encryption scheme. The process of group communication between the IoMT members is simulated and visualized by using NS3 software. The data for communication is evaluated by the performance metrics, viz. packet delivery ratio, throughput and delay. The proposed dual encryption scheme is shown to be highly secure and effective in this IoMT environment.

Key words: IoMT, Group Key, Dual Encryption, RSA, AES, NS3

1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) when they are used in the health care sectors for the acquisition of bio-signals (viz. ECG, EEG etc.) and physiological parameters (viz. BP, Body Temp., Heart rate, Blood Oxygen Level etc.) for analysis are termed as "Internet of Medical Things (IoMT)". This domain (IoMT) is playing vital role in medical services. The group communication between the members (doctors and devices /patients) of the IoMT network is very important and it is mandatory to set up a group key for secure communication. Nowadays, the group Communication between doctors, patients, caretakers, healthcare devices etc. is not secure in the network technology scenario.

In recent days, in order to maintain the authentication and security in IoMT networks, various cryptographic algorithms have been used. Hyper Elliptic Curve based Public Key Cryptography is used group key agreement for IoT Health Care System [1]. Key management is a main issue in Group Communication so it can be overcome by ECC Protocol in which no need to create the key for every transaction [2]. Decentralized lightweight group key management is proposed for ensuring secure data distribution and focusing on symmetric group key per sub group communication in IoT environment [3]. In order to avoid the malicious attack in the cloud computing, enhanced identity based encryption which generates an improved secure key in large-scale 5G networks [4]. Due to frequent changes in group membership, updating group key is difficult in highly dynamic networks like VANETs. To overcome this limitations, asymmetric light-weight multicast scalable (ALMS) group key management protocol is proposed [5]. Providing security against attack is the basic issue in MANETs, for which secure group key exchange and encryption mechanism is proposed [6].

The RSA algorithm implementation for encryption and decryption is described as cryptographic technique [7]. Implementing digital signature with RSA algorithm is proposed to enhance the data security in cloud computing [8]. The RSA algorithm along with pseudo noise sequence is utilized for the encryption of video information transfers [9]. The RSA algorithm is efficiently implemented for speech data encryption and decryption [10]. The performance of RSA, AES and DES algorithms is studied and compared for secure data transfer [11]. The high speed RSA algorithm has developed a new generation keys method, called RSA-Key Generation Offline and saved all the keys in the database [12]. A comparison of the AES and RSA encryption algorithms in image

encryption is made using MATLAB and shown that the AES algorithm has produced better results than the RSA algorithm [13].

A hybrid cryptosystem using RSA and Blowfish algorithms provides better security for cloud computing and the FPGA device is used for implementation [14]. The hybrid RSA and novel chaos based RNG (random number generator) algorithms are designed and implemented to perform strong encryption [15]. The DES and RSA hybrid encryption algorithm is more secure and easier for data transmission between Bluetooth devices [16]. A triple phase hybrid cryptography technique (AES, DES and m-RSA) is used in a wireless sensor network for more security [17].

The RSA algorithm in google cloud using cloud SQL for storing the data in a third party place is implemented to provide efficiency and security [18]. The image encryption scheme using Arnold map and RSA algorithm is effectively implemented for high security [19]. An enhanced RSA algorithm with variable key sizes is proposed to increase the strength of data security in cloud computing [20]. The distributed RSA algorithm based on Hadoop is designed and implemented for the encryption of massive data [21]. A novel image encryption using Arnold transform and asymmetric RSA algorithm is enhancing the security [22]. The Optimization of data encryption modeling using RSA cryptography algorithm is applied to send email quickly and safely [23]. A comparative analysis of AES and RSA algorithms in cloud computing for data security is discussed and the AES algorithm is found to be the first choice for the data storage [24].

A detailed study and analysis on the medical Internet of Things with big data, IoT and cloud computing is done for providing e-health services in secure manner [25]. A key management method like mutual authentication and secret key agreements is to establish secure communication in the IoT-based health care system [26]. In healthcare domain (i.e., IoMT), future challenges, benefits and applications are overviewed to help the researchers [27]. The attacks, security threats and countermeasures on IoMT have been surveyed for lightweight security mechanism [28]. In this proposed study a secure group key is generated for group communication in IoMT environment with dual encryption scheme.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe briefly the details of the proposed system and dual encryption scheme. The performance of the proposed system, which includes a group key generated by a dual encryption scheme, an IoMT environment simulated using the NS3 simulator and an evaluation of performance metrics viz. packet delivery ratio, throughput and delay are presented in Section 3. We highlight the conclusions in Section 4.

2. Details of Proposed System

In our study, the group key management plays vital in group communication. It includes group key generation and group manager for secure key for group communication.

2.1 Proposed Group Key Generator Model

The key distribution center (KDC) is a vital part of the cryptographic system. Normally the cryptographic keys are obtained from the KDC cloud. In order to improve the security of group communication, we generate the cryptographic keys on our own system by employing dual encryption scheme, proposed by us. This group key generator is designed in our system (calling it as GK_G) instead of KDC. This scheme is now implemented in IoMT environment. In this study, the proposed group key is created by the Group Manager (GM) for a two tier architecture comprising of doctors and devices /patients. The sensors are being attached with all the group members /components of the communication network. When a member newly enters into IoMT environment, it is added into respective categories [29]. The Dual encryption scheme which consists of AES and RSA algorithms, is utilized in this study. The GM first initializes the members of the network like creating the ID for doctors and devices /patients as shown in Fig.1.

The GM creates cryptographic keys in the encrypted form, in future these keys are called as Group Key (GK)s and they are sent to all the members of the communication network. Whenever anyone of the members joins or leaves the group, i.e., when a doctor or a device /patient leaves or joins the group, the GM will change the group key for security purpose. GM maintains the forward /backward secrecy. Forward secrecy means when a doctor or a device / patient leaves the group, they cannot obtain the future keys. Backward secrecy means the new group members cannot obtain their old group keys, used previously in the group [29].

Doctors have IDs of doctors and devices /patients as shown in Fig.1. If any doctor wants details of any patient /device, they have to send the message to GM. In turn, the GM checks a doctor ID and group key. If a doctor ID

and group key are confirmed, then only the requested details will be sent to the respective doctor.

DFD: Data Flow Diagram

Fig.1. Group key management framework

2.2 Proposed responsibilities of Group Manager

The different phases, handled by Group Manager are as follows.

When a new member joins the group: The group manager generates a user ID for the member, update the existing group key and communicate the new group key to all the members of the group. The shared key is utilized for further communication process [29].

When an existing member leaves the group: When a member leaves the group, update of the group key is communicated to the remaining members of the group. The user that leaves the group is no longer valid to communicate [29]. The responsibilities of GM as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2. Group Manager responsibilities

2.3 Dual Encryption Scheme

This study proposes a group key management approach with dual encryption scheme (AES and RSA) to ensure secure group communication.

2.3.1 AES Algorithm

It is a symmetric block algorithm, also known as Rijndael algorithm, the individual blocks of data are encrypted

by 128,192 or 256 bits [30]. The computation speed of AES algorithm was found to be at least 6 times faster than triple DES algorithm. The key size was low in DES algorithm so hackers can easily hack the key. The triple DES algorithm is an improved version of DES algorithm, however the speed was found to be low. The working principle of AES relies on the 'substitution-permutation network'. A sequence of operations is there in the AES model like some inputs are replaced with some outputs termed as substitutions. The inputs in some cases are shuffled and is termed as permutations. The byte based computation is performed by AES algorithm, 128 bits of data are processed in terms of 16 bytes. The 16 bytes of data are formulated in terms of the 4×4 matrix. The count of execution rounds in AES algorithm is a variable parameter and it relies on the length of the key. For 128 bits, 10 rounds of execution are utilized in AES, whereas for 192 bits of data requires 12 rounds of execution and for 256 bits of data requires 14 rounds of execution [31,32]. The AES framework is depicted in Fig.3.

Fig.3. AES framework

An AES Round is depicted in Fig.4. It comprises of four sub-phases as shown in the figure.

Fig.4. AES rounds

Description of Sub-phases of an AES Round:

Byte Substitution (Sub Bytes): The substitution of 16 bytes of data are formulated based on the fixed table (S-box). The outcome of the byte substitution is in the form of a matrix having four rows and columns.

Shift Rows: The left wise shift operation of the four rows are done, values that 'fall off' are inserted in the right side of the row. The shifting operation stages are as follows; shifting is not performed in the first row, second

row shifting is carried out by shifting one byte to the left, shifting on third row is carried out two positions to the left, shifting on fourth row is carried out three positions to the left

Mix Columns: Column wise shifting is carried out in the 4×4 matrix based on the permutation function. The resultant matrix comprises of shuffled values.

Add round key: The 128 bits of the data are then XORed with the 128 bits of the round key. After this process, it is checked whether it is the last round, last round in the sense the resultant output is the cipher text. On the other hand, if it is not the last round, then the above steps are repeated [30]. The diagrammatic representation of AES encryption is shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5. Flow diagram of AES encryption algorithm

2.3.2 RSA Algorithm

It is an asymmetric algorithm. It is a public key encryption framework and was found to be a secured one. The RSA algorithm utilizes private and public keys.

Step 1: Generation of the RSA modulus; the first stage begins with the 2 prime numbers a and b such that, their product is N.

$$N=a*b$$

Step 2: Derived Number (E) is formulated such that it is greater than 1 and less than a-1 and b-1. The primary constraint is that, no common factor of a-1 and b-1 except 1.

Step 3: The product value and derived number make the RSA public key.

The sender send the input message with the public key (N, E). S is a plain message- call it in form of number less than N. If S is greater than N then the message will be divided, encrypted and concatenate [31].

The expression for encryption of the data is as follows.

$$C=S^E \text{ mod } N$$

The diagrammatic representation of RSA encryption as shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6. Flow diagram of RSA encryption algorithm

2.3.3 Proposed Algorithm for Dual Encryption Scheme

The Dual encryption scheme is utilized in this work. The algorithm used for the dual encryption scheme is described below.

Dual Encryption scheme Process:

In dual encryption scheme the plain message is divided into left message L_Part and right message R_Part. L_Part is encrypted by using key AK in AES algorithm. After encryption EncLMsg will have 128 bits. R_Part is encrypted by using public key RPu in RSA algorithm. After encryption EncRMsg will have 128 bits. Both the L_Part and R_Part are indexed in the correct position and stored in FullEncryptMsg. The full encrypted message and encrypted key are compressed by using hash function. FullEncryptMsg will have 256 bits. Now this FullEncryptMsg is a group key distributed to members of communication network by group manager. Encryptkey are also compressed by using hash function and stored by the group manager for safety purpose [33].

The Mathematical model for the dual encryption process is given below in an equation form, which is similar to secure medical data transmission model, given in [34]

$$C = \{E_{AES}, E_{RSA}, M_{left}, M_{right}, K_{left}, K_{right}, AK, R_{Pu}\}$$

$$K_{left} = \{E_{AES}, (M_{left}, AK)\}$$

$$K_{right} = \{E_{RSA}, (M_{right}, R_{Pu})\}$$

$$E_{Key} = (AK, R_{Pu})$$

The steps in the dual encryption scheme are as follows.

Algorithm: Dual (AES & RSA) Encryption Scheme

Input : Plain Message(text /& numbers)

Output: Cipher Message, Key k

Begin

1. Dividing the Plain Message into two parts (L_Part, R_Part)
2. Generating new AES key AK
3. Encrypting EncLMsg= AES-128(L_Part, AK)
4. Generating new RSA key (Public R_{Pu})
5. Encrypting EncRMsg=RSA(R_Part, R_{Pu})
6. Build FullEncryptMsg by inserting both EncLMsg and EncRMsg in their indices
7. EncryptKey = (R_{Pu}, AK)
8. Compress FullEncryptMsg by convert to hash values
9. Compress EncryptKey by convert to hash values
10. Return FullEncMsg

End

Dual encryption scheme generates 256 bits of group key for group communication. When the members of communication network want to send or receive the data from other members of communication network, they can use this group key. They don't have to generate the key for every communication so the communication is very fast between them.

2.3.4 NS3 Simulator

This group communication is implemented for IoMT environment and is simulated using NS3 software. In this simulation 50 members of network are used as nodes. The IoMT comprises of remote monitoring of patient data, the devices of mimicking healthcare data and the users represent the physicians or radiologists who are in need of data for diagnosis and treatment planning.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Group Key generated by dual encryption scheme

The group key values are generated by dual encryption scheme. These group key values are unique. The time duration (t) for generation of group key sample values using dual encryption scheme are given below in Table.1.

Table.1. Key values for the dual encryption scheme in group communication

S. No.	Time stamp t (sec)	Group Key sample values
1	1.576	7b41c01f053d90a0879aba3c935abecdd68efd2e82543c471f229b0eed03b5f82c0fee908d33861f35453be6506a36c08e9e5e302b86c9bb5706506f30269f47b24ff111e585af4d7a38b0a33c1745212656e7270418345efb4e6a7e240cd0192b0505fc354477102ecc67e710d32f7aff84a5bb90537be34257b987e1295640h
2	1.573	7001d583665f47d0cd772901d0b49cc41e46581c5734faa025fcbf30d4e79179303571f4e46c8ea74c41186c90e4896ca40c5d4fe3112159a6da94a9db629e6a9d55e9ecd40f67de30cef26b0bbf96b28234a1a92b77f81903a22fd5c4540026515d99cb443dfd111ab919f97b1218fd88b8acf5c1e8502103a1f25b7 07a252dh
3	1.571	45bfdb12da54ef365f3cf82fde8529a18bad0420ca6f57cf807e268d67d9e10d12b478e5838d769aadf91403b77ddcec9b9fd77ade92e9d4858ff607912c98808d31dde1df805793194d5746016bf5072dcd7c33bf7c01b959a8073e496fdb1477ccd55cc530b72dff4be94a43c28db8cc569513009b992d8849c3ef a52ac4h

In IoMT Environment, strong authentication by GM and more secure key will prevent the security attacks like data theft, eavesdropping, privacy loss etc. Moreover, authentication mechanism must be more efficient and fast without comprising level of security [1].

A 256-bit encryption key is considered to be very secure and efficient. In fact, it is currently the standard for encryption in many industries and applications, including online banking, e-commerce and government communications. The strength of an encryption key is determined by the number of possible combinations that can be generated by the key. A 256-bit key offers a large number of possible combinations, specifically 2^{256} or approximately 1.16×10^{77} [1]. This means that it is virtually impossible for anyone to hack the encryption key using brute force methods or any other known cryptographic attacks. Hence a 256-bit encryption key is considered to be a very secure and efficient option for protecting sensitive information.

In our proposed study, we are using 256 bits as group key. When hackers try to use brute force attack to crack our group key, they must check maximum 3.403×10^{38} key combinations for 128 bit for AES Key part. The estimation of years to break AES 128 bits is 3.19×10^{14} [35]. But this is only the half part of the group key. The other part of the group key is having 128 bits, encrypted by RSA. It cannot be easily cracked by the hacker within weeks or months. The hackers will never guess that the dual encryption key scheme works with two different encryption algorithms while they are trying to hack the group key.

For the security purpose of group communication in IoMT environment, we propose one more constraint in Dual encryption scheme i.e., when the group key is not newly generated after 72 hours then group manager will generate a new group key.

Normally the hackers will intrude into the group key during the communication. There are two types of hackers, one is outside hacker, other one is inside hacker. The motivation of an outside hacker is to get group key or to share the duplicate group key to the group members. There are two ways for an outside hacker to endeavor their motivation. One way by grasping the channel between the group manager and GK_G. But it can be overcome since we are using dual encryption scheme which is not known by outside hackers. The second way is to get the group key from the members in the group communication [36]. But second way can also overcome by backward /forward secrecy method and group manager generate a new group key whenever members of communication network join or leave the group [29].

The motivation of inside hacker is to know the information of other members in the group [36]. But it is not possible because the members cannot communicate with each other; they can communicate only with group manager in the group. So our proposed dual encryption scheme is against outside and inside hackers. From this we can conclude that our proposed dual encryption scheme is secure for group communication in IoMT Environment.

3.2 Simulation Results

3.2.1 IoMT Environment simulated using NS3 Simulator

The group communication is implemented for IoMT environment and is simulated using NS3 software. In this simulation, 50 members of network are used as nodes. The sample group key distribution using dual encryption scheme are shown in Figs. 7, 8 and 9.

Fig.7. Sample group key distribution in the network from 31st node

Fig.8. Sample group key distribution in the network from 39th node

Fig.9. Sample group key distribution in the network from 40th node

3.2.2 Evaluation of Performance Metrics

The performance of the dual encryption scheme is validated by the metrics viz. packet delivery ratio (PDR), throughput and delay. The packet delivery ratio is the ratio between the number of packets, received at the destination and the number of packets, sent from the source. The throughput is a measure of how many packets per sec., successfully reached the destination. The delay (in sec) determines the lag in the arrival of packet to the destination. The group key, generated using our proposed scheme is compared with KDC key.

(a) Packet delivery ratio

The packet delivery ratio vs number of nodes plot is depicted in Fig.10. In the plot, the number of nodes is taken in the x-axis and the PDR (in %) is taken in the y-axis [37,38]. The proposed scheme performs the simulation by different number of nodes in the network to observe the effect on packet delivery ratio. The proposed scheme will select the path which has less inference and also consider the congestion in the nodes for selecting the route to deliver the data. Hence in the proposed scheme, more number of packets will be delivered to the destination when compared to KDC.

Fig.10. Packet delivery ratio vs number of nodes plot

(b) Throughput

The throughput vs number of nodes plot is depicted in Fig.11. In the plot, the number of nodes is taken in the x-axis and the throughput (kbps) is taken in the y-axis [37,38]. The proposed scheme will deliver the data in a specific time. Hence in the proposed scheme, the data will be delivered quickly to the destination when compared to KDC.

Fig.11. Throughput vs number of nodes plot

(c) Delay

The delay vs number of nodes plot is depicted in Fig.12. In the plot, the number of nodes is taken in the x-axis and the delay (in sec) is taken in the y-axis. The increase of congestion leads to increase of delay time. The less congestion path reduces the delay [37, 38]. The proposed scheme selects the path which has less congestion among the paths towards the destination nodes. Hence the proposed scheme performs better when compared to KDC.

Fig.12. Delay vs number of nodes plot

The Dual encryption scheme gives proficient results in generating the group key for group communication in

IoMT environment. The dual encryption scheme in the group communication ensures security in data communication. The outcome of this study gains prominence for Internet of Medical Things (IoMT). The telemedicine gains importance in the today's scenario, especially after the impact of COVID 19. The dual encryption scheme in this study ensures the secure transfer of medical data in IoMT environment.

4. Conclusions

The group communication in the Internet of Medical Things is an active area of experimental research. The security is vital when multiple devices /patients communicate with the group manager. In this study, the proposed dual encryption scheme has been efficiently implemented by generating the group keys for secure group communication in an IoMT environment. The process of group communication between the IoMT members is simulated and visualized by using NS3 software. This scheme has been validated by the performance metrics, viz. packet delivery ratio, throughput and delay. The outcome of this study paves a way towards the usage in IoMT environment. The healthcare institutions can utilize this proposed framework for transfer of medical data to the authenticated users in a secure way. The proposed dual encryption scheme is shown to be highly secure and effective in this IoMT environment.

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